

Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 25 June 2000

[\[CAIN Home\]](#)

[\[Key Events\]](#) [\[Key Issues\]](#) [\[Conflict Background\]](#)

PEACE: [\[Menu\]](#) [\[Summary\]](#) [\[Reading\]](#) [\[Background\]](#) [\[Chronology_1\]](#) [\[Chronology_2\]](#) [\[Chronology_3\]](#) [\[Article\]](#) [\[Agreement\]](#) [\[Sources\]](#)

Text: IICD ... Page Compiled: Martin Melaugh

STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
25 June 2000

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
---	---

Gentlemen:

President Martti Ahtisaari and Mr Cyril Ramaphosa informed the Commission today that they have successfully completed an initial inspection of several IRA weapons dumps. The two inspectors report that they were shown a substantial quantity of IRA arms, including explosives.

Moreover, the inspectors have ensured that the weapons are secure and cannot be used without their becoming aware that this has happened.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 25 June 2000

Dublin Office Dublin Castle Block M, Ship Street DUBLIN 2 Tel No: 00 353 (0)1 4780111 Fax No: 00 353 (0)1 4780600	Belfast Office Rosepark House Upper Newtownards Road BELFAST BT4 3NX Tel No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8600 Fax No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8601
--	--

[List of IICD Reports](#)

CAIN contains information and source material on the conflict and politics in Northern Ireland.
CAIN is based within Ulster University.